

Study on Assessment of Ocular Morbidity and Blindness in Diabetes Mellitus in Rural Population: A cross-sectional StudyVikas Kamat¹, Manoj Bhivate², Pramod Wartha³, Milind Sonone⁴¹Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Vedantaa Institute of Medical Sciences, Palghar²Associate Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Vedantaa Institute of Medical Sciences, Palghar³Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Vedantaa Institute of Medical Sciences, Palghar⁴Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Vedantaa Institute of Medical Sciences, Palghar

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Diabetes mellitus is an important metabolic disorder characterized by a raised blood glucose resulting from deficiency of insulin release and function. Diabetic microvascular complications in the eyes, especially diabetic retinopathy (DR) are an important cause of visual disability and blindness. Hence, the present study was conducted to assess ocular morbidity among diabetes mellitus patients in a tertiary care centre.

Material and Methodology: The present hospital based cross-sectional study was conducted at Department of Ophthalmology from March 2023 to February 2024. A total of 254 patients above 18 years who presented to hospital with Diabetes Mellitus were included in the study. Patients not giving a valid consent, pregnant women and women with gestational diabetes were excluded from the study. Permission from the Ethical Committee was taken prior to commencement of the study and informed written consent was taken from the participants of the study. Data entry and data analysis was done using MS Excel and epi info version 7.

Results: The mean age of patients was 48.21 ± 14.22 years with majority of females 143 (56.30%). The morbidity pattern among diabetes mellitus patients showed majority of patients had Visual impairment (17.72%) followed by Cataract (16.14%), Diabetic Retinopathy (12.2%), blindness (4.33%).

Conclusion: The ocular morbidity among diabetic patients was Visual impairment, Cataract, Diabetic Retinopathy and Blindness.

Keywords: Ocular Morbidity, Blindness, Diabetes Mellitus, Rural.

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Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is an important metabolic disorder characterized by a raised blood glucose levels resulting from deficiency of insulin release and its function. [1] India is set to emerge as the diabetic capital of the world. According to an estimate, over 74 million Indians were diagnosed with diabetes in 2021, and this is expected to rise to over 124 million by 2045, the largest number in any nation in the world. [2]

Macro and microvascular complications of long-standing diabetes have made it an important cause of morbidity, mortality and disability in affected people. These complications especially the microvascular complications can affect different organ systems of the body including the eyes. [3] Diabetic microvascular complications in the eyes, especially diabetic retinopathy (DR) are an important cause of visual disability and blindness and are thus gaining importance in the present era of a rapidly increasing number of diabetics throughout the globe. Reasons for loss of vision in

diabetics are diabetic maculopathy and complications of proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR). [4] Another common complication of diabetes is diabetic macular edema (DME), which is also a major cause of vision loss and, which can occur at any stage of DR. As per Wisconsin epidemiologic study of diabetic retinopathy (WESDR) at 20 years of duration of diabetes mellitus more than 60% of patients with type 2 diabetes and almost all patients with type 1 have some degree of retinopathy. [5] These estimates are expected to rise further due to the increasing prevalence of diabetes, ageing of the population and increase in life expectancy of those with diabetes. Because of the disproportionately large number of patients with type 2 diabetes (90%-95%), this group comprises a substantial proportion of patients with visual impairment secondary to diabetic retinopathy. [6]

Hence, the present study was conducted to assess ocular morbidity among diabetes mellitus patients in a tertiary care centre.

Objective: To assess ocular morbidity among diabetes mellitus patients in a tertiary care centre

Material and Methods

The present hospital based cross-sectional study was conducted at Department of Ophthalmology from March 2023 to February 2024. A total of 254 patients above 18 years who presented to hospital with Diabetes Mellitus were included in the study. Patients not giving a valid consent, pregnant women and women with gestational diabetes were excluded from the study.

Permission from the Ethical Committee was taken prior to commencement of the study and informed

written consent was taken from the participants of the study. Patient demographic and medical details was recorded in the proforma sheet along with the symptoms preceding the disease. The ophthalmic examination was done by a single ophthalmologist. Best corrected visual acuity for distance and near were recorded. Intraocular pressure was also documented. After dilation fundus examination of both eyes was done using Indirect Ophthalmoscope. Any changes attributable to diabetes were documented. All the recent investigations done from the same institute were also noted down in the questionnaire. Data entry and data analysis was done using MS Excel and epi info version 7 (available from WHO).

Results

Table 1: Demographic characteristics among patients: (n=254)

Variables		No of Patients (n=254)	Percentage
Age	18-30	28	11.02
	31-50	68	26.77
	51-70	99	38.98
	>70	59	23.23
Gender	Male	111	43.70
	Female	143	56.30
Education	Illiterate	28	11.02
	Literate	226	88.98
Socioeconomic Status	Class I	21	8.27
	Class II	61	24.02
	Class III	89	35.04
	Class IV	48	18.90
	Class V	35	13.78

A total of 254 patients were included during the study period. The mean age of patients was 48.21 ±14.22 years with majority in age group 51-70 years (38.98%). Among 254 patients, most of the

patients were females 143 (56.30%) followed by males 111 (43.70%). The majority of patients were literate 226 (88.98%) and belongs to Class III socioeconomic status (35.04%). (Table no.1)

Table 2: Disease characteristics among patients: (n=254)

Variables		No of Patients	Percentage
Type of Diabetes Mellitus	Type I	03	1.18
	Type II	251	98.82
Duration of Diabetes Mellitus (Years)	<5	58	22.83
	5-10	149	58.66
	>10	47	18.51
Control of Diabetes Mellitus	Controlled (HbA1c <6.5%)	96	37.80
	Un-controlled (HbA1c ≥6.5%)	158	62.20

Among 254 patients with Diabetes Mellitus, most of them belong to Type 2 DM (98.83%) The majority of patients had duration of DM with 5-10 years (58.66%) and 96 (37.8%) patients had Controlled Diabetes Mellitus. (Table no.2)

Table 3: Ocular Morbidity among patients: (n=254)

Ocular Morbidity	No of Patients*	Percentage
Visual impairment	45	17.72
Blindness	11	4.33
Diabetic Retinopathy	31	12.20

Cataract	41	16.14
Glaucoma	8	3.15
Dry eye syndrome	7	2.76
Diabetic Keratopathy	5	1.97
No morbidity	158	62.20

(*Multiple response present)

The morbidity pattern among diabetes mellitus patients showed majority of patients had Visual impairment (17.72%) followed by Cataract (16.14%), Diabetic Retinopathy (12.2%), Blindness (4.33%) and Diabetic Keratopathy (1.97%). (Table 3) No morbidity among patients was found in 158 (62.2%) patients.

Table 4: Relation of demographic characteristics and Ocular morbidity among patients: (n=254)

Variables		Ocular Morbidity		P value*
		Present (n=96) (%)	Absent (n=158) (%)	
Age	18-30	04 (4.16)	24 (15.19)	X ² =35.39 P<0.0001
	31-50	10 (10.42)	58 (36.71)	
	51-70	51 (53.12)	48 (30.38)	
	>70	31 (32.29)	28 (17.72)	
Gender	Male	56 (58.33)	55 (34.81)	X ² =13.43 P<0.0001
	Female	40 (41.67)	103 (65.19)	
Education	Illiterate	18 (18.75)	10 (6.33)	X ² =9.39 P=0.001
	Literate	78 (81.25)	148 (93.67)	
Socioeconomic Status	Class I	10 (10.42)	11 (6.96)	X ² =5.82 P=0.21
	Class II	23 (23.95)	38 (24.05)	
	Class III	42 (43.75)	47 (29.75)	
	Class IV	22 (22.92)	26 (16.45)	
	Class V	09 (9.38)	26 (16.45)	

(*P value <0.05 statistically significant by Chi square test)

The relation of demographic characteristics and ocular co-morbidity showed elderly age, males and illiterate patients were more prone for ocular morbidity with statistically significant difference. (P<0.05)

Table 5: Relation of disease characteristics and Ocular morbidity among patients: (n=254)

Variables		Ocular Morbidity		P value
		Present (n=96)	Absent (n=158)	
Type of Diabetes Mellitus	Type I	02 (2.08)	01 (0.64)	X ² =1.07 P=0.33
	Type II	94 (97.92)	157 (99.37)	
Duration of Diabetes Mellitus (Years)	<5	21 (21.88)	37 (23.42)	X ² =27.32 P<0.0001
	5-10	39 (40.62)	110 (69.62)	
	>10	36 (37.50)	11 (6.96)	
Control of Diabetes Mellitus	Controlled (HbA1c <6.5%)	25 (26.04)	71 (44.94)	X ² =9.06 P=0.001
	Un-controlled (HbA1c ≥6.5%)	71 (73.96)	87 (55.06)	

(*P value <0.05 statistically significant by Chi square test)

The relation of disease characteristics and ocular co-morbidity showed greater duration of diabetes mellitus and uncontrolled Diabetes Mellitus patients were more prone for ocular morbidity with statistically significant difference. (P<0.05)

Discussion

The present hospital based cross-sectional study was conducted to assess ocular morbidity among diabetes mellitus patients in a tertiary care centre. In the present study, mean age of patients was 48.21 ±14.22 years with majority in age group 51-70 years (38.98%). Among 254 patients, most of the patients were females 143 (56.30%) followed by

males 111 (43.70%). The majority of patients were literate 226 (88.98%) and belong to Class III socioeconomic status (35.04%). (Table no.1) Fazili AB et al.[7] in a study ocular morbidity among diabetics observed mean age of patients was 53.13±10.85 years with 136 (65.7%) were females and only 71 (34.3%) were males, similar to the present study. The study group was similar to that of the study conducted by Qureshi T et al. [8] from Kashmir, where 61.6% females and 38.4% males participated. Gadkari SS et al.[9] in their study reported a preponderance of males (61.2%) and 88.6% were between 40 and 80 years of age. This finding contrasted with the present study. Similarly,

Idiculla J et al.[10] also reported a higher proportion of males (63.6%) in their study, with an age range of 32-85 yrs and mean (SD) of 56.41(+9.91) years. In the present study, among 254 patients with Diabetes Mellitus most of them belong to Type 2 DM (98.83%). The majority of patients had duration of DM with 5-10 years (58.66%) and 96 (37.8%) patients had Controlled Diabetes Mellitus. (Table no.2) Fazili AB et al.[7] observed majority 206(99.5%) of them had type 2 diabetes mellitus only 1 (0.5%) had type 1 diabetes mellitus. 110(53.1%) were diagnosed 15 years. Investigations showed that 125(60.4%) of them had controlled blood sugars and 82(39.6%) had uncontrolled blood sugars. The study was also in accordance with the study conducted by Qureshi T et al.[8] where 98% had NIDDM and only 2% had IDDM.

In the present study, the morbidity pattern among diabetes mellitus patients showed majority of patients had Visual impairment (17.72%) followed by Cataract (16.14%), Diabetic Retinopathy (12.2%), Blindness (4.33%) and Diabetic Keratopathy (1.97%). (Table 3)

No morbidity among patients was found in 158 (62.2%) patients. In accordance to our results lower prevalence was seen in studies conducted by Raman R et al.[11] (18.1%), Rema M et al.[12] (17.6%), Namperumalsamy P et al.[13] (10.6%) and Dandona L et al.[14] (22.58%) The results showed that of Qureshi T et al.(8) and Narendran V et al.[15] where prevalence of diabetic retinopathy (DR) was found to be 27% and 26.2% respectively, which was higher than the present study. Fazili AB et al.[7] in a study found Cataract was present in 13(6.3%) of the participants.

In the present study, the relation of demographic characteristics and ocular co-morbidity showed elderly age, males and illiterate patients were more prone for ocular morbidity with statistically significant difference ($P < 0.05$).

Similarly, the relation of disease characteristics and ocular co-morbidity showed greater duration of diabetes mellitus and uncontrolled diabetes mellitus patients were more prone for ocular morbidity with statistically significant difference. ($P < 0.05$) Qureshi T et al.[8] in their study observed that the prevalence of any DR increased with years duration of diabetes similar to Yau JWY et al.[16] meta-analysis.

In Kai S et al.[6] study, it was found that no patient with duration of diabetes less than 5 years had retinopathy, 73 patients (67% of those with retinopathy) were with duration of diabetes between 12- 21 years. Fazili AB et al.[7] in a study, ocular morbidity among diabetics observed higher prevalence of DR was found in those participants with uncontrolled blood sugar or HbA1c $> 6.5\%$.

This highlights that strict glycaemic control is much more effective in preventing or delaying the onset of DR.

Conclusion

The ocular morbidity among diabetic patients was Visual impairment, Cataract, Diabetic Retinopathy and blindness. Further, the risk factors like elderly age, uncontrolled blood sugar levels and duration of diabetes mellitus for ocular morbidity among diabetic patients. Besides regular retinal examinations, good metabolic control is indispensable for reducing the risk of ophthalmic complications in diabetics.

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